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Executive Summary:

The large-scale deployment of renewable energy sources introduces new challenges to the electricity grid due to the variable and intermittent nature of energy production. In this context, Europe needs to improve cross-border electricity interconnections in order to achieve its climate and energy goals. The European Union's electricity grid is already the most interconnected continental power network in the world. Moreover, interconnection capacities are mandated to be no lower than 10% of total energy production for all member states by 2020.

Both gas and electricity networks will play a key role in supporting the uptake of new technologies and meeting decarbonization challenges. In this regard, the integration of the electricity and gas sectors can optimise the assessment and usage of both grids, whilst continuing to meet the European energy policy objectives of sustainability, security of energy supply and competitiveness. Thus, the report aims to review the existing interconnection capacity between the island of Ireland and neighbouring territories, and new interconnection projects that have been proposed by several consortia. Both electricity and gas interconnections are evaluated and their potential for facilitating energy exports is discussed.

As of today, the existing interconnectors and those under development offer limited energy export capability. However, this may change in the future. First, the deployment of new interconnections will impose a downward pressure on the electricity prices of Ireland that will influence the dominant flow direction on the electricity interconnectors. Furthermore, higher penetration of renewable energy sources into the Irish electricity grid will diminish the dependency on imported natural gas, consequently, opening opportunities for exporting gas through its existing gas interconnectors.

Alternatively, hydrogen can be used as an energy carrier to export the excess energy produced from Ireland's vast offshore renewable resources. Hydrogen can be produced, transported and then converted back to electricity using fuel cells in its final destination, or it can be exported as a fuel to be used as an end product e.g. in the transport sector.

List of Abbreviations

- AC – Alternating Current
- BETTA – British Electricity Trading and Transmissions Arrangements
- CEF – Connecting Europe Facility
- DC – Direct Current
- EWIC – East West Interconnector
- FTRs – Financial Transmission Rights Options
- GB – Great Britain
- HVAC – High Voltage Alternating Current
- HVDC – High Voltage Direct Current
- IGBTs – Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistors
- INEA – Innovation and Networks Executive Agency
- IRC – Integrated Return Conductor
- LCC – Line Commutated Convertor
- LNG – Liquid Natural Gas
- PCI – Project of Common Interest
- SEAI – Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
- SEM – Single Electricity Market
- SNIP – Scotland-Northern Ireland Pipeline
- TSO – Transmission System Operator
- TYNDP – European Ten-Year Network Development Plan
- VSC – Voltage Source Converter

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1 Introduction

The large-scale deployment of renewable energy sources such as wind or solar introduces new challenges to the electricity grid due to their variable and intermittent nature of energy production. In other words, the fluctuation of energy production over time and the possible mismatch between production and demand bring uncertainty regarding the resource requirements for maintaining power balance on the electricity grid. One possible solution to this problem is to increase the number of grid interconnections. Distant locations often have different demand load patterns that facilitates matching energy production and demand, thus reducing levels of wasted energy, e.g. wind curtailment, and therefore allowing higher penetration of renewable energy sources.

To enable higher penetration of renewable energy sources, interconnection capacities in all European member states are mandated to be no lower than 10% of their installed power generation capacity by 2020 (European Commission, 2016) and 15% by 2030 (European Commission, 2017). In other words, each country should have cables with enough total capacity to transport 10% of the electricity produced by its power plants across its borders to neighbouring countries. The European Union's electricity grid is already the most interconnected continental power network in the world. Based on the latest data from ENTSO-E, there are 82 electric interconnections between the EU and its ten neighbouring countries (ENTSO-E, 2018). The electrical system in Europe works on 50 Hz and, in continental Europe, it forms a single synchronous A/C grid where all member states share the responsibility of balancing the grid. Interconnection capacities already reach up to 40% of installed power generation in countries such as Denmark or Austria (Lajoie, 2018).

In this context, although Ireland has one of the best offshore wind resources in the world, the country has to increase ancillary services and energy storage capacities and/or deploy new interconnectors in order to support higher penetration of renewables. A single synchronous system operates on the island of Ireland. Currently, Ireland has 1 GW of installed electricity interconnection capacity, all of this with the neighbouring Great Britain system which represents slightly less than 10% of Ireland's electricity power generation capacity. Ireland is therefore on the way to achieve the European targets for interconnection capacities. In addition, the potential for energy generation is considerably larger than the current domestic demand, which opens the potential of exporting energy to other countries.

The gas network will also play a key role in supporting the uptake of new technologies and meeting energy system decarbonization challenges. For this reason, the integration of the electricity and gas sectors can optimise the assessment and usage of both grids, whilst continuing to meet the European energy policy objectives of sustainability, security of energy supply and competitiveness (ENTSO-E and ENTSOG, 2019).

Thus, this report aims to outline the existing and proposed interconnection capacities between the island of Ireland and neighbouring territories. Both electricity and gas interconnections are evaluated and their potential for facilitating energy exports is discussed.

The report is divided into six sections: Section 1 explains the context of the current report; Section 2 reviews the technologies and discusses characteristics, infrastructure, import/export capacities and reliability of existing and future electricity interconnectors; Section 3 outlines Ireland's existing and future gas interconnections and describes their characteristics, infrastructure, import/export

capacities and reliability; Section 4 presents the costs related to the implementation of new interconnectors; Section 5 summarises and analyses the energy exporting capability of the Island of Ireland; Section 6 presents the conclusions and recommendations for future interconnection development in the context of the island of Ireland.

2 Island of Ireland electricity interconnections

This section firstly reviews the electricity transmission technologies currently available. This will be necessary to describe Ireland's existing and developing electricity interconnections. In addition, the interconnections characteristics, infrastructure, import/export capacities and reliability are discussed.

2.1 Electricity interconnection technology review

Although several technical solutions for electricity transmission are available today, they are all based on two principles: High Voltage Alternating Current (HVAC) and High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC). Both technologies are widely deployed in electricity transmission networks. However, for the reasons explained on Section 2.1.2, this report is concerned for the most part with HVDC transmission systems.

2.1.1 High Voltage Alternating Current

HVAC technology is the most common electric power transmission technology used today. Alternating Current (AC) systems are usually characterized by their frequency. Currently, most AC networks in the world operate at either 50 Hz or 60 Hz nominal power frequency, which is kept constant within the system at all time (Friends of the Supergrid, 2012). In order to connect two AC systems, not only the frequencies have to be the same but both networks have to be kept synchronous. In other words, the systems have to maintain synchronisation of their frequency and phase.

In general, the main components required for HVAC transmissions are substations and lines/cables. Substations have the purpose of transforming the voltage of the electrical system. They can be either "step-up" or "step-down", meaning that they transform a generated power to a higher voltage for transport or to a lower voltage for distribution and consumption. Cables in AC systems, which have three phases, are composed of three conductors together as these systems require one conductor per phase. The transmission can utilize either overhead or underground cables. For underground cables, aluminium and copper are the most common conductor materials used (Friends of the Supergrid, 2012).

2.1.2 High Voltage Direct Current

HVDC is a mature technology and it has been commercially available since the early 1950's with the deployment of the first HVDC connection in Sweden. HVDC transmissions are advantageous for long-distance bulk-power delivery, asynchronous interconnections and long submarine cables (Bahrman and Johnson, 2007). **Figure 1** illustrates the investment cost in relation to the connection distance. The expensive rectifier and inverter stations for AC/DC and DC/AC conversion, which are not required in HVAC cases, significantly add to the overall cost of HVDC terminals (Alassi *et al.*, 2019). However, due to large losses over long distance of HVAC transmission lines and because HVDC requires fewer

cables/conductors, the transmission cost of HVDC is cheaper (Friends of the Supergrid, 2012). Consequently, once a critical distance is reached, HVDC systems become more attractive than HVAC from an economic point of view. The HVDC breakeven distance estimations vary but typically ranges from 300 to 800 km for overhead lines and between 50 and 100 km for offshore/underground cables (Alassi *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1 – Investment costs over distance for HVAC and HVDC transmission systems (ABB, 2019).

Currently, two basic converter technologies are used in HVDC transmission systems. These are Line Commutated Converter (LCC) and Voltage Source Converter (VSC). LCC is the more mature of the two technologies and is characterised by the use of thyristors for converting current from DC to AC or vice versa. On the other hand, VSC systems are more recent, with the first deployments on the late 1990's. This technology utilizes Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs) in its operation. Overall, LCC are used where very high capacity and efficiency are needed whereas VCC are deployed for interconnecting weak AC systems, large-scale variable and/or intermittent power to the grid or when the HVDC line is likely to be expanded to become a multi-terminal in the future (Alassi *et al.*, 2019). **Table 1** - Comparison between HVDC transmission options (Alassi *et al.*, 2019). compares both technologies and summarizes their main characteristics.

Table 1 - Comparison between HVDC transmission options (Alassi *et al.*, 2019).

	LCC	VSC
Switching device	Thyristors (1970's – present)	IGBT (1990's – present)
Commutation (frequency range)	Line dependent (50-60 Hz)	Self-commutated (up to few kHz)
Station power loss	0.6-0.8%	~1%
Power-flow reversal mechanism	Voltage polarity reversal (Slow, causes more current stress)	Current direction reversal (Fast, adds more reliability)
Network strength dependency	Dependent	Largely independent
Converter station footprint	Larger	Smaller (40-50%)
Inherent VAR consumption	50-60% if rated MW	None, and can support reactive power to AC grid
Reactive/filtering equipment requirements	High (Expensive)	Low
Inherent VAR control and grid support	No	Yes
Inherent AC grid black-start capability	No	Yes
Fault handling capability (AC side)	Lower (Line-frequency dependent)	Higher (MVAR support/black start)
Fault handling capability (DC side)	Higher (DC Reactor/SC failure)	Lower (High di/dt rate)
AC and DC side harmonics level	Higher	Lower
Market share 2018 (n° of projects)	70%	30%
Max available rating combinations	12,000 MW/ ~1100 kV	2000 MW/ ~500 kV
Common applications	High-power, long distances	Offshore/cable-based projects
Multi-terminal HVDC suitability	Limited	Highly suitable
Stations cost (High ratings)	Lower	Higher

2.2 Existing electricity interconnectors

2.2.1 East West Interconnector

EirGrid owns the East West Interconnector (EWIC) which has linked the electricity grids of Ireland and Great Britain (GB) since 2012. The EWIC is a HVDC connection capable of providing capacity of 500 MW, flowing in either direction (import / export), and is one of the largest HVDC schemes in the world to use VSC technology. The cables are 262 km long, of which 76 km is underground and 186 km is submarine cable. The land and submarine cable technical specifications are described in **Table 2**. The system holds a spare cable that allows immediate response and quicker recovery times in the event of a fault. They are also buried for most of their extension to avoid damage from anchors or trawling activities.

Table 2 – Technical specification of the EWIC. Adapted from (EirGrid, 2019c).

	<p>Submarine cable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extruded polymer insulated cable • Conductor 1650 mm² copper • Steel armouring • Diameter 117mm • Weight 39 kg/m 		
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2.2.2 Moyle interconnector

The Moyle interconnector is owned by Mutual Energy and it links Scotland and Northern Ireland with a total capacity of 500 MW. The interconnector consists of two monopolar HVDC cables operating in parallel with a power rating of 250 MW in either direction (**Figure 2**. Each cable system consists of 55 km of subsea cables and 8.5 km of underground cables (Harvey, Stenseth and Wohlmuth, 2001).

Figure 2 – Moyle interconnector general arrangement (Mutual Energy, 2014).

The cables use the Integrated Return Conductor technology (IRC). This design has a metallic coaxial layer integrated in the HVDC cable to form the return path for the current and also to serve as a part of the torsion balanced armouring (Harvey, Stenseth and Wohlmuth, 2001). The IRCs have failed twice since they were commissioned. The first fault happened in August 2011. The interconnector went out of service and after repairs the cables became operational with limited capacity of 450MW in February 2012 (Mutual Energy, 2011). Following further faults, a major part of the interconnector had to be taken out of service and after laying separate return conductors their full operational capacity was restored in 2016 (Mutual Energy, 2014)(Mutual Energy, 2016). In February 2017, the cable suffered another fault, halving reduced capacity of 250 MW. Full capacity was restored in September 2017, following repairs by Nexans.

Although the capacity of the Moyle interconnector is 500MW, Mutual Energy originally only applied for a transmission entry capacity of 80MW in the direction Northern Ireland to GB due primarily to the fact that anticipated flows for their customers were expected to be in the opposite direction (i.e. GB to Northern Ireland) for the majority of the time, but also because of constraints on the transmission networks at either end of the interconnector. However, increased demand for flows west to east driven by the penetration of renewables is expected. At present, the Northern Ireland to Scotland export capacity is 300MW and can only be securely accommodated under certain dispatch scenarios (Moyle Interconnector Limited, 2017). **Table 3** summarises the expected capacity available to the Moyle interconnector in the GB network. These values also vary slightly to maintain system stability (EirGrid, 2019b).

Table 3 – Summary of capacity available to Moyle in the GB network (Mutual Energy, 2019a).

Direction	Dates	Contracted capacity (MW)
West to East	10 Nov 2017 to 30 Nov 2019	80
	01 Dec 2019 to 31 May 2020	307
	01 Jun 2020 to 31 Oct 2021	250
	01 Nov 2021 to 31 Mar 2022	160
	01 Apr 2022 onwards	500
East to West	All year long	450

2.3 Electricity interconnectors being proposed or developed by utilities and energy companies

2.3.1 Greenlink interconnector

Greenlink is a proposed subsea and underground electricity interconnector cable linking Ireland and GB having a nominal capacity of 500 MW. Greenlink will provide a new grid connection between the EirGrid transmission network in County Wexford (Ireland) and the GB network in Pembrokeshire (Wales). The power will be able to flow in either direction, depending on supply and demand in each country. The project will connect the two substations through HVDC cables. Detailed environmental and technical assessment surveys commenced in 2018. This followed the completion of desk-based assessments and consultation with statutory consultees. The Greenlink interconnector is currently in the public consultation stage and it aims to commence construction by 2020 (Greenlink, 2019).

2.3.2 Celtic Interconnector

The Celtic Interconnector is a proposed electrical link which if built will enable the exchange of power between Ireland and France. EirGrid (Ireland’s TSO) and Réseau de Transport d’Electricité (France’s TSO) carried out a series of studies to investigate the feasibility of the electrical link between the two countries. As part of the feasibility study, potential routing between the south coast of Ireland and the north-west coast of France was considered for the Celtic Interconnector. The length of the subsea cable would be approximately 500 km. The total length of the interconnector between the two countries would be approximately 575 km. The industry standard for interconnectors of this length is HVDC. If built, the Celtic Interconnector will bring the following benefits (EirGrid, 2019a):

“(i) Ability to import and export 700 MW of electricity; (ii) Enhanced security of supply for Irish electricity users as it will provide Ireland’s only direct energy connection to an EU Member State once the United Kingdom leaves the EU; (iii) Apply downward pressure on the cost of electricity to consumers in Ireland; (iv) Allow greater integration of low carbon electricity generation in both countries; (v) Provide a direct fibre optic communications link between Ireland and France.”

The project is currently in Step 4 (correct as of April 2020) of the EirGrid’s six-step consultation process. The most recent public consultation had the objective to shortlist one proposed landfall location on the coast of East Cork and three proposed sites and cable routes for a converter station in East Cork. The timeline for the Celtic interconnector project is given in **Table 4**.

Table 4 - Celtic interconnector project expected timeline (Réseau de Transport d’Electricité (RTE), 2019).

Activity	Timeline
Consultation	2018 – 2019
Impact Assessment and public inquiry	2019 – 2020
Authorisations	2022
Procurement and work	2022 – 2025
Tests and commissioning	2026

2.3.3 Other projects

There are many proposed interconnector projects involving the isle of Ireland. **Table 5** contains a list of projects that has been assessed as part of the next European Ten-Year Network Development Plan (TYNDP). Because these projects are at a preliminary stage and have not been proposed for the TYNDP 2020, they were not described in this report¹.

Table 5 - Proposed interconnection projects unlikely to go further.

Project	Timeline
Gallant	Interconnection with GB
Greenconnect	Interconnection with GB
Greenwire North	Interconnection with GB
Greenwire South	Interconnection with GB
Irish-Scottish Links on Energy Study (ISLES)	Offshore wind hub potentially providing interconnection to Scotland
Organic Power	Interconnection with GB

2.4 Trading arrangements

Beginning in 2018, the new all-island Integrated Single Electricity Market (I-SEM) is coupled with the British Electricity Trading and Transmissions Arrangements (BETTA) market. In other words, the physical interconnector flows are determined by the relative prices in the two connected markets. Therefore, both EWIC and the Moyle interconnector offer long-term transmission rights in the form of

¹ <https://tyndp.entsoe.eu/news/2020/02/148-pan-european-electricity-transmission-projects-and-25-storage-projects-in-the-tynd-p2020/>

Financial Transmission Rights (FTRs), which give the holder the right to a financial pay-out based on the difference in day-ahead prices between the I-SEM and BETTA markets (EirGrid, 2019c; Mutual Energy, 2019a).

The trading in both interconnectors is based on two trading schemes, explicit auctions and implicit auctions. The explicit auctions allow market participants to purchase the right to utilise capacity on the interconnector from one day up to one year ahead of the delivery day. On the other hand, the implicit auctions allow market participants to purchase capacity and the associated energy on the EWIC in one transaction for individual 30-minute interval periods of the trade day markets (EirGrid, 2019c; Mutual Energy, 2019a).

3 Island of Ireland gas interconnections

This section outlines Ireland's existing and future gas interconnections and describes their characteristics, infrastructure, import/export capacities, and reliability. It is worth mentioning that the capacities for gas interconnectors are normally shared as million cubic meters per day (mcmd). In order to make this comparable with the electricity interconnectors, these capacities were all converted to GW in this report. The conversion was based on the following steps (the example is based on Moffat's capacity):

1. 1 m³ of Natural Gas (NG) equals to 11.11 kWh;
2. If the maximum capacity of the interconnector is 31 mcmd, this is equivalent to 344.4 GWh/day;
3. Dividing 344.4 GWh/day by the 24 hours in a day we obtain the capacity of approximately 14 GW.

3.1 Existing gas interconnectors

3.1.1 Moffat entry point

Moffat is Ireland's primary gas entry point and it connects the Irish natural gas system to the national gas grid system in GB. Moffat allows for the importation of GB gas to Ireland via two sub-sea Interconnectors and an onshore transmission network in Scotland. This entry point between GB and Ireland is unidirectional, as gas can only flow physically from Scotland to the three markets downstream (i.e. Ireland, Northern Ireland, and the Isle of Man). The interconnector subsea pipelines (IC1 and IC2) are made of steel having diameters of 24" and 30" respectively. IC1 is mostly responsible for supplying the Republic of Ireland network whereas IC2 mainly provides natural gas to Northern Ireland and the Isle of Man (Commission for Regulation of Utilities, 2018).

The maximum theoretical capacity of the Moffat entry point is 31 mcmd (14 GW). However, the interconnector is operating below its maximum capacity that was approximately 10 mcmd (4.8 GW) in 2018 (Gas Networks Ireland, 2018). Although the Moffat entry point is currently physically unidirectional with gas flowing from GB to Ireland, the Project PCI 5.1.1 is proposing to turn it into a bi-directional link. Gas Networks Ireland was allocated funding by the EU Commission for feasibility studies for physical reverse flow at Moffat following a successful application through the EU Innovation

and Networks Executive Agency (INEA). Funding of 50% of the total budget for the feasibility studies was granted under the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), the maximum grant allowed for studies (Gas Networks Ireland, 2019).

3.1.2 Scotland-Northern Ireland Pipeline (SNIP)

The Scotland-Northern Ireland Pipeline (SNIP) is a unidirectional pipeline with 24" in diameter and 135 km length along with the local transmission pipelines. The maximum contractual capacity is 8.68 mcmd (4 GW) flowing from Scotland to Northern Ireland. Physical reverse flow of the SNIP is planned, including pipework modifications to allow bi-directional metering and flow control as well as moving the gas odourisation point to a new point(s) downstream of the bi-directional transmission system. The project has achieved PCI status. The planned transmission capacity is 132 GWh/d (5.5 GW) and the compressor station will have an installed power of 10 MW (Utility Regulator, 2015; Mutual Energy, 2019b).

3.2 Proposed gas interconnectors

3.2.1 Shannon LNG

Shannon LNG is a natural gas terminal proposal. The project will consist of up to four Liquid Natural Gas (LNG) storage tanks, each with storage capacity of 200,000 cubic metres (2.22 GWh) and a jetty capable of receiving the largest LNG tankers in operation. Shannon LNG has planning permission to build an LNG import terminal with gas send-out capacity of up to 28.3 mcmd (13 GW) (Shannon LNG, 2019). Phase 1 of the project will have send-out capacity of 17 mcmd (7.8 GW) whereas Phase 2 will add more 11.3 mcmd (5.2 GW) send-out capacity.

The project is currently suffering from public opposition due to the origin of the LNG transported into the terminal (fracked gas). Concerns are that the construction of the terminal will result in Ireland importing fracked gas from US, despite this technique being banned in Ireland. Another argument is that the project will slow down the development of renewable energy sources in the country (McDermott, 2019).

4 Discussion

Figure 3 – Existing and proposed electrical and gas interconnectors in the island of Ireland. Map created by Jared Peters and Felix Butschek. illustrates the existing and proposed electrical and gas interconnectors for the whole island of Ireland. A summary of their capacities and project timeframes are also presented in **Figure 4** and **Table 6**. Together, the figures and table provide visualization of the geographic distribution of the interconnectors and the capacity development timeframe for the whole island. The future capacities described in this report also agree with EirGrid forecasted interconnection capacities (EirGrid, 2019d). Currently, Ireland has a total electricity interconnection capacity of 1GW and there is the potential to have up to 1.95GW additional capacity installed by 2026, with a strong likelihood that the Celtic Interconnector project will go ahead, adding 700 MW capacity between Ireland and France. The Island of Ireland also has two gas interconnections with GB that together account for up to 18 GW of gas interconnection capacity. This capacity can be expanded if the Shannon

LNG project goes forward. It is worth noticing that this report is taking an all-island perspective and therefore the North-South interconnector is not described in the report.

Figure 3 – Existing and proposed electrical and gas interconnectors in the island of Ireland. Map created by Jared Peters and Felix Butschek.

Figure 4 – Electricity and gas interconnection capacity forecast.

Table 6 – Present and future interconnectors capacity of the isle of Ireland.

Interconnectors	Power capacity	Commissioned/Expected
Electric		
Moyle	500MW	2001
East West	500MW	2012
Greenlink	500MW	2023
Celtic	700MW	2026
Gas		
Moffat	14GW	1993
SNIP	4GW	1996
Shannon LNG (Phase 1)	7.8GW	2025
Shannon LNG (Phase 2)	5.2GW	2030

The operation of electricity interconnectors is subjected to electricity market dynamics. Thus, the electricity interconnection capacities cannot be considered as energy exporting potential. In fact, the electricity price of each node of the interconnector is what decides in which direction the electricity is most likely to flow. As the electricity price changes according to different supply and demand scenarios, the electricity direction changes accordingly. Between Ireland, GB and France (potential future connection), the highest average electricity price is in Ireland. Therefore, electricity will be imported rather than exported in the existing and proposed interconnectors in the short-term.

Regarding gas interconnections, at present, their main purpose is to import natural gas to supply the Irish domestic market. Recently a project aiming to reverse the capacity of the Moffat entry point was proposed which will allow Ireland to export NG. In practice, the amount of gas exported will be significantly lower than the imported. This is because Moffat will be the main source of natural gas for

Ireland due to the decommissioning of the Inch entry point (Kinsale gas field) in 2020 and the reduced production in the Corrib gas field. Although the Moffat interconnector is able to supply current and future demands of gas to Ireland, this brings serious concerns regarding security of supply as NG imports from Moffat will account for approximately 86% of annual gas system demands by 2026 (Gas Networks Ireland, 2018).

In this context, converting energy from new renewable power plants into hydrogen could represent an interesting option for Ireland. Hydrogen can enable greater integration between the electrical and gas networks, it can be used as energy carrier to export energy, and it can also be commercialized as a fuel. Integrating the electrical and gas networks and adding energy export capability are paramount to support higher penetration of renewable energy sources in Ireland. Furthermore, higher penetration of renewable energy sources would reduce the dependency of NG from Moffat which would increase security of supply and potentially allow gas exports through its pipelines. However, due to the time in which the pipelines were deployed, is unlikely that they are able to transport hydrogen.

In addition, the Shannon LNG project it is being strongly criticized from the allegation that it would support the continues use of fossil fuels and this could delay the energy transition in Ireland. From this argument, there could be an interesting opportunity to explore the potential for Shannon LNG to become a hydrogen terminal.

5 Conclusion and recommendations

This report reviewed the existing and proposed interconnection capacities between the island of Ireland and neighbouring territories. Electricity and gas interconnections were evaluated and their potential for facilitating energy exports was discussed.

As of today, the existing and developing interconnectors represent limited energy exporting capability. However, this may change in the future. On one hand, present electricity prices in Ireland tend to be higher than in neighbouring countries. The deployment of new interconnectors will facilitate the import of cheaper electricity from abroad and therefore will exert downward pressure on electricity prices in Ireland. On the other hand, higher penetration of renewable energy sources into the Irish electricity market will diminish Ireland's dependency on imported NG. Consequently, this will open room for exporting NG through its existing gas interconnectors.

Alternatively, the conversion of electricity into hydrogen could provide benefits to the Irish energy market as a whole. The development of a hydrogen market in Ireland could increase the integration between electrical and gas networks. It would bring increased security of supply by potentially lowering gas imports, and it would support higher penetration of renewable energy sources into the overall Irish energy market. It could also introduce alternative means of exporting energy via hydrogen tankers, as interconnectors have limited capacity to do it.

5.1 Proposed future work

5.1.1 Inefficient operation of interconnectors

Currently, there are examples of inefficient operation of interconnectors, e.g. the Moyle Interconnector has been shown to be importing power while at the same time NI wind farms are being constrained/curtailed. Therefore, it is worth investigating the mechanisms behind why this is allowed to happen, if the same happens in the EWIC, and if it is likely to happen for the Celtic and Greenlink interconnectors (personal communication, Sara Armstrong).

5.1.2 Future interconnection vs system services capacities

Due to the operational challenges that come with higher penetration of renewable energy sources, higher interconnection and/or system services capacities are required. However, to estimate transmission expansion requirements, an accurate forecast of load patterns, generation capacities and the resulting power flows for short and long-term scenarios is needed. As there are several factors that have to be considered for carrying out this analysis, the solution of this optimization problem involves a high degree of complexity. Furthermore, not only the reinforcements required need to be calculated but also the appropriate timing of building the assets has to be considered.

Currently, methodologies to forecast the requirements for either interconnectors or system services are widely available. However, as far as the researchers are concerned, transmission expansion planning methodologies that consider the deployment of interconnectors and system services simultaneously have not yet been developed. The implementation of a robust optimization tool for transmission expansion planning that considers both solutions would maximize the benefits from the implementation of new infrastructures therefore reduce overall infrastructure costs.

5.1.3 Breakeven distance for hydrogen as energy carrier

Interconnections linking distant locations are very costly. Therefore, finding alternative cost-efficient solutions for the transport of energy can result in substantial overall project cost savings. In this context, Taieb and Shaaban (Taieb and Shaaban, 2019) performed an economic analysis comparing HVDC transmission systems and hydrogen pipelines for the transport of energy from offshore wind farms to coast. The cost-distance sensitivity analysis illustrates that hydrogen pipeline systems are less expensive than HVDC for distances larger than 740 km. Their work also showed that the losses of HVDC transmission lines are higher than using hydrogen pipelines for distances higher than 510 km.

Their study used a rather simple analysis for the break-even distance calculation and the variations of certain parameters used for their analysis could result in significantly different results. For this reason, the development of a more robust sensitivity analysis of the break-even distance in which the transport of hydrogen becomes more economically attractive than HVDC interconnectors is required. In addition, not only hydrogen pipelines but also the transport of hydrogen, or fuels derived from hydrogen, using carrier vessels must be considered.

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